

Weakness Analysis – The Mystical Fifth Force of Nature – 8T

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Abstract:

In this paper, broad analysis of the new 8-Theory, a varying curvature framework which manifested in a varying Lorenz manifold, $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. Such a manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. The arbitrary variation term has been discretized and partitioned $\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ to create threefold combination of two distinct elements varying in a. The second equation is the coupling constant series, which describe the propagation bosonic fields from fermion clusters, analysis of the weakness of the framework will be made. In particular, the biggest weakness is the lack of evidence for a fifth force of nature, standing at a magnitude of 1/850 with the coupling of the strong. It is the ultimate test, despite the framework already predicted the fine structure constant value, it will validate that there are infinite amount of bosonic field, isomorphic to primes or (+1).

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

As a varying topology over time, independently from the metric. It is a separate space, which $\partial g / \partial t$ do not obey the same rules as the metric. $\partial M / \partial g$ Varying metric according to a varying topology. The term describes the bosonic and fermionic fields manifesting in our metric, as we can associate bosonic ripple based on the variation of the second term from the right. $\partial s / \partial M$ How does the varying metric effect the manifold itself $s = (M, g_E)$. $\partial L / \partial s$ The last term, how does the varying manifold effect the dimension of length. It is a varying curvature framework in which arbitrary variation vanish into matter, and net variations on the manifold are isomorphic to bosonic propagations. We partitioned and discretized the term $\delta g = 0$ and after doing so, derived that there must be an even amount of two distinct elements that differ in sign and form a group due to their varying nature.

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$0: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0 \quad (1.181)$$

We proved that in order to bring the element back to where it was and to attach it to itself it takes an additional map on the varying element, to a threefold combination.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1 \quad (1.182)$$

$$\delta g_1(0)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1 \quad (1.183)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.01)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.011)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (2.012)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

The $2N(\)$ terms refer to a hadronic structure, perfectly symmetrical to vanish into matter, as it is two and three divisible. The invariant (3) element is a symmetry-breaking operator causing a destabilization. Such a factor than yields a net variation, N_V , isomorphic to primes or one, and associated with bosonic propagation fields, which are infinite in kind. The next Boson in the coupling constant series should stand at ratio of $1/850$ relative to the strong interaction. That is relatively strong compared to the gravitational coupling constant. The force is about 6.65 weaker than the electric, so taken from that point of view compared to the gravitational it is immensely stronger. If we were able to detect Gravitational waves, we should be able to detect the new element in the series. The implicit axiom is that each element in the series is manifested in a form of a wave. It is the major test of the 8-theory, whether There is an additional force of nature and if there is – whether the magnitudes are Matching. Are there any experimental indications for a fifth force in particle detectors? Experimental physicist views are vital for analysis of this weakness. It is the ultimate test for the theory, and if validated we have found the theory of everything.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)